

The benefit of open access (OA) for researchers in lower-income countries: Tracing evidence through analyses of reference patterns

Henrik Karlstrøm,¹ Fredrik N. Piro², and Dag W. Aksnes³

¹ henrik.karlstrom@nifu.no, ² fredrik.piro@nifu.no, ³ dag.w.aksnes@nifu.no

NIFU – Nordic Institute for studies in Innovation, Research and Education, Økernveien 9, 0653 Oslo (Norway)

Introduction

Making scientific literature freely available to everyone is a main objective of the open access (OA) movement. This may be of particular importance for researchers in lower-income countries where access literature often has been hindered by high subscription costs.

Several recent studies have explored country and regional differences in OA publishing, with a low-income perspective in mind, both from the producing side, finding that lower-income countries have the highest shares of OA publishing (e.g., Iyandemye & Thomas, 2019), and from the consuming side, the highest share of OA citations (Simard et al., 2022). Our study is grounded in the latter perspective. We explore whether researchers from lower-income countries tend to refer to fewer previous publications when they publish and how this pattern evolves over time. Additionally, we investigate whether researchers from lower-income countries rely more heavily on literature that is openly available through various OA routes compared to researchers in other countries.

Data and Methods

The study is based on Web of Science (WoS) data. The analyses have been carried out at a global level. Because transnational collaborations make it impossible to identify the country source of a given reference in a publication, the study is limited to regular articles with only one single author country, in total 32.7 mill. articles during the period 1980-2020 and 1.29 billion references in the reference lists of these articles.

Data on OA status is retrieved from the Unpaywall database. We considered all forms of OA as one category for the purposes of this study. We are classifying author countries into four income groups (“high”, “upper middle”, “lower middle” and “low” income), based on the World Bank’s classification of countries.

Results

The number of references per article has increased considerably during the period 1980-2020. In 1980 an average article contained 19.8 references compared with 43.2 in 2020. Figure 1 shows that

articles from high-income countries have many more references on average than publications from other income groups. This holds over the entire 40-year period, but the gap has been reduced in recent years. Interestingly, there are relatively small differences across the groups of low- and middle-income countries.

Figure 1. Average number of references per publication, 1980-2020, by country income group.

Within the period under consideration another trend has happened concurrently with the increase in the number of references per paper – the growth of openly available scientific publications. The study shows that the proportion of references which are OA is increasing over time for all publications and all country groups.

In 2005, publications from high-income countries had on average 7.5 OA references and 24.2 non-OA references (Table 1). These numbers increased to 16.5 OA and 30.3 non-OA references in 2020. Thus, the growth is stronger for OA than for non-OA references in absolute as well as relative terms. A similar pattern is shown for middle- and low-income countries.

Table 1. Average number of references per publication, 2005-2020, by country income group and access type.

	High-income		Middle/low-income	
	Non-OA	OA	Non-OA	OA
2005	24.2	7.5	18.6	7.4
2020	30.3	16.5	20.0	8.5

2007	25.5	7.9	20.4	7.6
2008	26.5	8.2	21.0	8.2
2009	27.0	8.7	20.8	7.9
2010	28.6	9.3	22.0	8.1
2011	29.3	9.7	22.5	8.2
2012	29.5	10.0	23.3	9.2
2013	29.7	10.4	23.5	8.9
2014	30.2	10.9	24.3	9.5
2015	30.2	11.4	24.3	10.3
2016	30.2	12.4	25.2	10.7
2017	30.5	13.3	25.7	11.6
2018	30.4	14.1	26.2	12.5
2019	30.5	15.4	26.3	13.2
2020	30.3	16.5	26.9	14.9

Table 2 demonstrates that the compound average growth rate (CAGR) is positive for both types of references, but highest for OA references for all income groups, and highest for the two lowest income groups.

The increased growth rate of OA references, particularly among publications from lower-income countries, indicates a convergence of reference practices between researchers from different income groups.

Table 2. Compound Average Growth Rate by income group and access type of references, 2005-2020.

Income group	Non-OA	OA
Low-income	35 %	42 %
Lower middle-income	28 %	33 %
Upper middle-income	26 %	32 %
High-income	13 %	18 %

The calculations have also been carried out at field levels. This analysis reveals that the overall OA patterns identified for groups of countries are present also at field levels. However, in some fields, the patterns do not follow the general tendencies for country groups, making the conclusions less generic.

Discussion and Conclusions

We observe that in the period coinciding with the rise of the open access movement, researchers in lower-income countries have closed some of the gap in the length of reference lists of their publications. While not providing any causal evidence for the effect of open access on reference practices, we believe this development can at least partly be explained by a larger increase in references to open access publications from the lower-income countries than from the high-income countries. The lower-income countries have a much stronger compound growth rate than high-income countries for both closed and open literature, but the increase is clearly highest for the open access publications. This suggests that the rise of OA publishing has been particularly beneficial for researchers in lower-income countries. In this way a

fundamental objective as well as justification of the OA movement has been accomplished.

However, changing the costs of publishing from subscription fees to author payments (Budzinski et al., 2020), has also sparked a discussion about whether lower-income countries, as producers of research, would be disadvantaged by no longer being affordable to publish in journals (Nature, 2022)

References

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